
SOME CONSIDERATIONS ABOUT THE IRRIGATION NETWORKS OF KOKAN KHAN

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Annotatsiya: This article covers the construction of irrigation facilities and the emergence of new agricultural centers near the city of Kokand and in various parts of the khanate.

Keywords: Koqan, Fergana Valley, thousand, Koqansoy, “Anjumat at-Tawarikh”, Abdurahimkhan, Olimkhan, Tepakorgan, Kaynar, Saray, Targoba, Chomochbi, Janiksit, Pillakhona, Pirtak, Andijan, Namangan, “Tasnifi Gharib” Khudoyorkhan.

Fergana Valley is one of the regions of Uzbekistan where the first agriculture was formed and developed. It should be noted that the development of irrigated agriculture led to the formation of certain centers and the construction of various irrigation networks in the valley region in different historical periods. Information related to the farming of the Min clan, which founded the Kokan Khanate, and the construction of irrigation networks by the rulers of the dynasty has reached us through a number of historical sources. The information related to the development of Kokand and its surrounding lands by the Ming clan is described in the book "Historical Shahruhi" by Mulla Niyaz Muhammad. According to his information, during the reign of Altinbeshikkhan, farmers of five or six villages around Kokan were divided into three groups, two groups used Kokansoy, and one group used Naymansoy for irrigation purposes [1.306-307].

Consideration. According to the above historical source, the current city of Kokand and its surrounding lands were intensively developed starting from the 17th century. In the work "Afzal al-Tavorikh", Tangriyor sultan started digging a new canal in the west of Kokan by involving specialists of irrigation facilities on the

instructions of his father Oltinbeshikkhan. The construction work lasted for four years. At that time, the irrigation facility was operated under the name of Oltinbeshikkhan, but now it is named after Naymansoy [2.26]. As a result of the construction of this canal, a number of small villages and agricultural areas were established for ten years in the lands up to the banks of the Syrdarya. Tangriyor Khan attracted many masters and craftsmen to these areas, and large villages appeared along this canal. At that time, Kokansoy, which now flows through the territory of Kokan city, was called Kattasoy.

During Tangriyor Khan's reign, the lands around the village of Targova were appropriated thanks to the anhor released from Kattasoy. Thus, in the 17th and 18th centuries, rapid exploitation of Kokan and its surrounding lands began. It can be considered that this process had a certain influence on the transformation of the city of Kokhan into the center of the Fergana Valley in the later period. According to the author of the work "Anjumat al-Tawarikh", Abdurahim Khan, the son of Shahrukhbi, the founder of the Thousand Dynasty, established large irrigation networks in the Ferghana Valley after returning from the Samarkand campaign with victory. A year after the victory campaign of Erdanabi from the Kokan Khans, a canal was dug that reached the areas from the Sokh River to the Syrdarya. During the reign of Norbotabi, a canal was built from the Sokh River and a number of villages and settlements were built on its banks. Olim Khan dug six canals during his reign. As a result, one of the largest villages of Fergana, Altiariq, was established, and the displaced people from different regions were provided with work tools at the expense of the treasury. In the work "History of Shohruhy" information was given about the existence of villages such as Targoba, Chomochbiy, Janiksit, Pillakhona, Pirtak, Tepakorgon, Kaynar, Saray, Turalgir located around Kokhansoy. Therefore, at the turn of the XVII-XVIII centuries, the construction of many irrigation networks in Kokan and its surroundings led to the emergence of farming villages here.

At the beginning of the 19th century, the large territory of Yermachit was acquired by the Kokhan Khans. In his work, Muhammed Khakim Khan gives information about Umar Khan's development works in this area. This area, located

one farsakh west of Kokan, made up four thousand tanobs of land and attracted Umar Khan's attention with its wonderful nature [1.166]. Such natural reserves of the Kokan khans were also established between Margilan, Andijan and Namangan.

During the reign of Khudoyar Khan, as a result of the construction of the Ulughnakhr irrigation facility, the territories from the villages of Asaka and Karatepa in the west to Syrdarya were appropriated and turned into agricultural centers. All affairs in Shahri Khan and Asaka were entrusted to Saint Isa, one of Khudoyar Khan's confidants [1.167]. According to the author of "Tasnifi Gharib", Khudoyar Khan built water tanks in Asaka along with the construction of Ulughnakhar. Development of Asaka and its surrounding lands led to the development of trade relations and the implementation of construction activities. In 1847, Khan entrusted 21 people to use the land in this area and the surrounding areas. Also, Khudoyar Khan built a madrasa here, and the land here was given as a waqf. In 1840, Muhammad Ali Khan gave the right to use the Yabu mine to four sons of Muhammad Alim Khan. During the period of the following khans, the right to use these works was left to the representatives of this house [1.168-169]. As a result of the construction of irrigation networks, check estates were established. According to Middendorf, one of the Russian authors, a farm with 600 yards was established in the village of Yangichek. 70 water mills were built in Ulughnahr. 1130 courtyards were established in the territory of Ulughnahr on the lands appropriated during the reign of Khudoyar Khan. From 1848 to 1878, 6 large settlements were established in this area. A number of canals were made from the Akbura river. In 1868, Khudoyor Khan built a network of irrigation facilities in the Uchkurgan region.

In the 19th century, it was impossible to determine the borders of the city due to the spread of irrigation networks, the establishment of gardens and vineyards in and around the city of Kokand, and the dense population of the city and surrounding districts, one of the participants of the event reports. In the 1960s and 1970s, there were 1,214 villages in the Fergana Valley (except Khojand), of which 360 were located around Kokan. [1.172-173]. In the 30s of the 19th century, horticulture, viticulture, cotton growing, animal husbandry, crafts, and trade developed rapidly in

this area. Cultivation began in the 50s of this century. Yermachit region became one of the most prosperous regions. The villages of Gumaili, Dangara, Qizilmush, Sariosiya, Amirabad around Kokan were adapted to rice cultivation [3.89].

Summary. it can be concluded that the construction of irrigation facilities in various lands of the Kokan Khanate led to the formation of new agricultural centers, the emergence of a large agricultural center around the city of Kokan from the seventeenth century. Although the issues related to the economic situation of this period have been preserved in the written sources of the khanate period, they have not been sufficiently studied. A detailed study of the information provided in written sources would have enriched the history of Kokan.

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